

eScience Center Fellowship Programme 2024: Application Form

Esther Plomp 8 April – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10939832>

December 2023

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

This document contains explanatory text in italics. Please remove this text before submission.

1a. Details of the fellowship applicant

Surname, first name, title(s)	Plomp, Esther, Dr.
Email address	e.plomp@tudelft.nl
Institute	Delft University of Technology
Department	Faculty of Applied Sciences
Section	Management support
Address	Lorentzweg 1
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City	Delft

1b. What is your current occupation / career stage?

Data steward

2a. Title of your proposed fellowship plan

Tracking Research Objects at the Faculty of Applied Sciences, TU Delft

2b. Summary for the eScience Center website (max 150 words)

Please provide a non-expert summary of the plan for use on the eScience Center website and other media.

Please take into account that the proposal summary provided and the summary for non-experts, may be used for publication purposes, should your application be awarded, and that it will be subject to editing.

Evaluation of researcher performance is currently a contested subject within academia. Although many researchers contribute to their field of expertise in a multitude of manners, the most stringent criteria of success is the number of research articles published. Subverting the current “publish or perish” culture requires a novel approach to the evaluation of research objects (such as software, data and methods) other than research articles. However, there is currently no standardised way to track such research objects. This project aims to identify and quantify the role of research objects, in particular research software, within the Faculty of Applied Sciences at TU Delft and evaluate how these are being shared within the research community. By monitoring open research objects such as software, the project aims to stimulate an open research culture and incentivise scientists to adhere to Open Science practices and the FAIR principles.

2c. In which of the four categories below does your project fit most closely?

Please rank the four disciplines in order of relevance to your project (1: most closely related to your project, 4: least related to your project). This will be used to partner you with the most relevant point of contact at the eScience Center.

Discipline	Rank
Environment and sustainability	2
Natural sciences and engineering	1
Life sciences	3
Social sciences and humanities	4

FELLOWSHIP PROJECT PLAN

3. Project plan

Please paste the text of your project plan here. The text and illustrations should facilitate easy reading and should be self-contained. The plan should be a proposal for a project that improves the state of research software (max 1500 words including references). This must include:

1. A reflection on the awareness and/or use of research software in the academic community, discipline, or field of the applicant.
2. A description of the applicant's objectives related to improving research software.
3. A description of any activities that will be undertaken to achieve the applicant's objectives.
4. A justification of why the applicant is well situated to execute the planned activities, and act as an ambassador for research software.

Evaluation of researcher performance is currently a contested subject within academia. Although many researchers contribute to their field of expertise in a multitude of manners, the most stringent criteria of success is the number of research articles published. Subverting the current “publish or perish” culture requires a novel approach to the evaluation of research objects (such as software, data and methods) other than research articles. Current tracking of research outputs or objects is often limited to research articles, as other research objects (such as data, software and methods) are only more recently shared, cited and properly indexed in a manner that would allow systematic tracking. Notable exceptions are the [Charité Metrics Dashboard](#) (using [ODDPub](#)) and the [French Open Science monitor](#) (using [GROBID](#) and [softcite](#)).

Several journals have also shared their efforts on tracking research objects, such as Science (which [kept track of which data repositories were used by authors](#)), and PLOS ONE ([sharing information on preprint, data and code sharing](#)) (see also [Federer et al. 2018](#); [Federer 2022](#)). While PLOS ONE is sharing the resulting data, the methods used by both publishers are not publicly available and the resulting information is only relevant for their particular journal. Other research efforts have investigated data and code availability for their disciplines, such as ecology ([Culina et al. 2020](#)), social sciences ([Hardwicke et al. 2020](#)), biomedical sciences (Riedel et al. 2020; [Serghiou et al. 2021](#)), paleogenetics ([Anagnostou et al. 2015](#)) and astronomy ([Pepe et al. 2014](#)). There are also scraping tools available that can collect the required data for research object tracking from BioMedCentral ([BiomedCentral scrapper](#), not updated since 2019, see also [Gabelica et al. 2022](#) based on BioMedCentral data). All of these solutions do not cover the needs of the Faculty of Applied Sciences and are difficult to reuse for other institutes for their own purposes. Furthermore, only Culina et al. 2020, Riedel et al.

2020, and Serghiou et al. 2021 shared the underlying code in accordance with the FAIR principles, allowing for reuse of the code for other purposes.

At the Faculty of Applied Sciences we have a high percentage of Open Access publications (98 % for 2023). Nevertheless, how well we are doing in terms of open data, code and methods is currently difficult to assess as there is very limited data available. From a preliminary manual analysis from research articles from 2018 it appeared that data and code is only available for less than 5% of the research articles published, and in the majority of these cases it is not shared in accordance with the FAIR principles. Manual analysis of these research articles is labour intensive and not sustainable. Therefore, the current project aims to establish a semi-automated workflow to analyse publications based on their DOIs and keywords such as “data” “code” “method” “data repository”, “available”, “DOI”, as well as data repositories regularly used by researchers of the faculty (4TU.ResearchData, Zenodo, ENA, EVA, SRA, UniProtKB, IDR, EMPIAR).

The aim of the proposed project is to analyse all articles and software repositories published by researchers of the Faculty of Applied Sciences in 2023 to be able to assess where the Faculty stands in terms of sharing research objects. This information can be used to increase awareness and deliver guidelines to improve the quality of research objects sharing. Ideally, a semi-automatic workflow is set up in a manner that most of the information needed can be extracted from the DOIs of the articles published in that year, or that information can be retrieved from software repositories via GitHub/Lab usernames or organisation names. Ultimately, this project contributes to building a more robust and trustworthy research ecosystem, where knowledge is freely exchanged, collaborations are facilitated, and the reproducibility of scientific findings is prioritised.

The applicant is well situated to execute this project, as she contributed to the TU Delft Research Software policy (Akhmerov et al. 2021) and guidance document (Bazuine 2021). As a Data Steward of the Faculty of Applied Sciences, the applicant has access to information needed for this project, such as information on researchers/labs and their publications and software repositories. The applicant is familiar with FAIR principles for research software as a contributor to the FAIR principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles, Chue Hong et al. 2022). The script/workflow is ideally set up in R, the programming language that the applicant is most familiar with. The applicant is involved in promoting Open Science at the Faculty level (for example, setting up a Research Data Management policy for the faculty level and coordinating an Open Science Team (TNW Open Science Team 2023)), and is therefore ideally situated within the Faculty to improve the awareness for sharing research software. This project will also have a positive impact on research software sharing beyond the Faculty of Applied Sciences, as the resulting workflow can be shared and reused in accordance with the FAIR principles, as well as any resulting guidelines that aim to improve the current research object sharing practices. The applicant aims to share the results, software repository and the guidelines during the Dutch Open Science Festival (22 October 2024), as well as the Research Data Alliance Plenary (11-15 November 2024).

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- Bazuine, M. (2021). TU Delft Guidelines on Research Software: Licensing, Registration and Commercialisation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4629635>
- Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F. E., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P. A., Honeyman, T., Struck, A., Lee, A., Loewe, A., van Werkhoven, B., Jones, C., Garijo, D., **Plomp, E.**, Genova, F., ... RDA FAIR4RS WG. (2022). FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles) (1.0). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>
- Culina A, van den Berg I, Evans S, Sánchez-Tójar A (2020) Low availability of code in ecology: A call for urgent action. *PLoS Biol*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000763>
- Federer LM (2022) Long-term availability of data associated with articles in PLOS ONE. *PLoS ONE*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0272845>
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- Serghiou S, Contopoulos-Ioannidis DG, Boyack KW, Riedel N, Wallach JD, Ioannidis JPA (2021) Assessment of transparency indicators across the biomedical literature: How open is open? *PLoS Biol*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001107>
- TNW Open Science Team. (2023). Faculty of Applied Science and Open Science – A team: Overview 2021-2023 (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7641319>

4. Fellowship timeline

Please provide a realistic timeline, running between June 2024 and end of May 2025, that demonstrates when you will plan and undertake the activities that are part of your project plan. The timeline may need to be adjusted during the project; this will always happen in consultation between the Fellow and the eScience Center.

Activity	Timeline
Set up dataset for workflow (applicant)	May-June
Set up workflow with eScience Center	June-September
Apply workflow to earlier years, or extended 2023 dataset, with eScience Center	October (may potentially be moved after October)
Present work at Open Science Festival with eScience Center	1-22 October 2024 (festival = 22 October)
Present work at RDA plenary	11-15 November 2024
Apply workflow to 2024 dataset	February - April 2025

5. Fellowship budget specification

Please paste a budget that specifies how your personal fellowship budget will be used below. The budget should outline how the personal budget of **€2,000 + 40 hours of eScience Center expertise** (“in-kind support”) will be used: the plan should outline the expenses and consumables the budget will cover in the form of declared costs. In addition, the plan should outline how eScience Center employee time is expected to be used. It should be clear from the plan that these hours are directly relevant to the proposed activities. Hours can be used at different times throughout the year, or all at once, for several eScience Center employees simultaneously.

Expenses and consumables	Financial budget up to €2,000
Open Science Festival travel and accommodation	€35,28 (train) + €280 (accommodation for two nights) + €30 (food expenses) = €345.28
RDA conference and travel costs	€600 (expected conference fee) + €1000 (expected conference travel costs) = €1,600.00
Total	€1945,28

In-kind support	Hours of eScience Center up to 40 hours
Support with development of the script/workflow to analyse the 2023 dataset	~27 hours ideally between June-September 2024
Support with refining/testing the script/workflow	5 hours in October 2024
Co-attendance for the Open Science Festival (optional)	3 hours (excluding traveling time and full day festival) on 22 October 2024
Applying the script/workflow to 2024 data (potential updates/consultation needed)	5 hours in February – April 2025
Total	40 hours

ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

6. Statements by the applicant

The eScience Center strictly applies the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU (see www.eugdpr.org). In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants must strictly apply these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (available at www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

- I endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG), as well as the underlying principles (GDPR).
- I endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP. **If 'NO', then please justify, and contact the eScience Center before submitting the application.**
- I have completed this form truthfully.

Name: Esther Plomp

Place: Utrecht

Date: 8 April 2024

To submit your application, send the completed form to fellowship@esciencecenter.nl. The deadline for application is 08 April, 2024, 14:00 CET.

Turn to the next page for an optional section.

OTHER INFORMATION (OPTIONAL)

7. A little more about you

The following section is *optional and will not affect your application*. Only share this information if you wish to share it. At the eScience Center, we are interested in the backgrounds of our project partners and future fellows. Therefore, we have a few questions about you.

7a. Which of the following disciplines are relevant to the research / work you do on a daily basis?

- Chemistry
- Earth Sciences
- Humanities
- Physical Sciences
- Research Support

7b. What gender do you identify as?

- Female

7c. In which country did you complete the majority of your education? The Netherlands

7d. What is your nationality? Dutch

7e. Your GitHub, Twitter, and / or LinkedIn accounts: <https://github.com/EstherPlomp/>
<https://www.linkedin.com/in/estherplomp/> / <https://scholar.social/@toothFAIRy>